

Tianjin Institute of Agriculture Resource and Environment

Analysis Report

Rwquester	Nankai University	Report number	HJ-F-FX-202012-013
Sample name	Soil samples	Date of receipt	December 3th, 2020
		Date of report	January 6th, 2021
Analysis items	Mechanical composition,pH,Organic matter,Cation exchange capacity		
Number of samples	Soil 1	Soil 2	
pH	8.39	5.46	
Cation exchange capacity (cmol ⁺ /kg)	7.3	14.4	
Organic matter(g/kg)	19.4	8.37	
Sample status	Brown ,lupm	Brown ,lupm	
Mechanical composition	Texture class(g/kg)		
Soil 1	1-2mm(g/kg)	7.95	
	0.5-1mm(g/kg)	24.6	
	0.25-0.5mm(g/kg)	23.3	
	0.05-0.02mm(g/kg)	79.0	
	0.02-0.002mm(g/kg)	286	
	<0.02mm(g/kg)	282	
	0.25-0.05mm(g/kg)	297	
	2.0-0.05mm(g/kg)	353	
	0.05-0.002mm(g/kg)	365	
Soil 2	1-2mm(g/kg)	0.750	
	0.5-1mm(g/kg)	3.81	
	0.25-0.5mm(g/kg)	7.08	
	0.05-0.02mm(g/kg)	125	
	0.02-0.002mm(g/kg)	179	
	<0.02mm(g/kg)	105	
	0.25-0.05mm(g/kg)	579	
	2.0-0.05mm(g/kg)	591	
	0.05-0.002mm(g/kg)	304	